

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15608025

An Assessment of Environmental Management through Industrial Ecology: Strategies and Impact

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ABSTRACT

The environment is an evergreen subject, as it plays important role in the healthy living and the existence of life on planet earth. The planet Earth is a home for different living species and all these species are dependent on the environment for food, air, water, and other needs. Through archival research analysis we were able to discuss the Importance of the environment, Environmental protection, Environment Management techniques, the Importance of Environmental Management, the Environmental management Model alongside the Environmental management systems. We further discussed the Industrial Ecology, its features, principles and benefits as well as tools to support industrial ecology as well as the approaches to industrial ecology and we finally made recommendations for further development.

Keywords: Industrial ecology, planet Earth, environment management, environmental protection

INTRODUCTION

All the living and non-living factors affecting an organism and ultimately determining its form and survival are known as Environment. The environment is an evergreen subject, as it plays important role in the healthy living and the existence of life on planet earth. The planet Earth is a home for different living species and all these species are dependent on the environment for food, air, water, and other needs. Our life support systems entirely rely on the well-being of every organism living on planet earth. This is why a lot has been written and spoken about the protection and conservation of the environment. There are even high-value courses dedicated to the study of the environment. A typical example is an environmental science. Environmental science is a field that deals with the study of the interaction between human systems and natural systems. Natural systems involve the earth itself and life (Salmi, 2003).

To Haloui & Yang (2024), Environmental science and engineering provide an integrated and interdisciplinary approach to the study of environmental problems using the knowledge of environmental concepts and ecology. Humans are a part of the natural environment. Unfortunately, over the years we have not yet learnt to moderate our activities in such a way as to help the environment. Human activities have often led to degradation of the environment. Big business gave a lot of things to the people but they are also impacting to the environments. So, that's why the environmental related studies came to the existence. Environment protection is an important perspective in the current scenario.

Environmental stress has been noted to be becoming severe day by day. Haloui & Yang (2024) further added that the level of Degradation of environment poses a serious threat to mankind. Different approaches are used to assure environmental protection among them environmental management and industrial ecology. Environmental management means the activity undertaken to monitor various organizations activities and wastage to make sure that will not impact negatively on the environment and or the human health. Therefore, industrial ecology is an environmental concept developed by researchers to improve environmental management (Tibbs, 1992).

Statement of the Problem

The increasing industrialization and consumption of natural resources have led to significant environmental degradation, pollution, and loss of biodiversity, with traditional industrial practices often prioritizing economic growth over environmental sustainability. This has resulted in severe environmental impacts, including climate change, air and water pollution, soil degradation, and loss of ecosystem services, posing significant challenges to sustainable development. Effective environmental management is crucial to mitigate these impacts, yet many industries struggle to balance economic growth with environmental sustainability, highlighting the need for innovative approaches like industrial ecology to transform industrial practices and promote sustainability.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study is to assess environmental management through industrial ecology: strategies and impact. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Investigate the impacts of industries on the environment.
2. Assess the importance, models, and system of environmental management.
3. Examine the concept and principles of industrial ecology.
4. Assess the approaches, constraints and incentives for industrial ecology.

Research Questions

The following research question gives direction to the study:

1. How do industries impacts on the environment?
2. What are the importance, models, and system of environmental management?
3. What is industrial ecology and the principles of industrial ecology?
4. What are the approaches, constraints and incentives for industrial ecology?

Significance of the Study

The study on "Environmental Management through Industrial Ecology" holds significant importance for several reasons:

1. Sustainable Development: The study contributes to achieving sustainable development by exploring ways to balance economic growth with environmental sustainability.
2. Environmental Conservation: By applying industrial ecology principles, the study aims to reduce environmental impacts, conserve natural resources, and promote eco-friendly practices.
3. Industrial Transformation: The study provides insights into transforming industrial practices, enabling industries to adopt more sustainable and environmentally responsible approaches.
4. Policy and Decision-Making: The findings can inform policymakers, industry stakeholders, and decision-makers about effective strategies for environmental management and sustainable development.
5. Future Generations: By promoting sustainable industrial practices, the study contributes to ensuring a healthier environment and more sustainable future for generations to come.

Scope

The study focuses on the impacts of industries on the environment, importance, models, and system of environmental management, concept and principles of industrial ecology, and approaches, constraints and incentives for industrial ecology.

Literature Review

Human activities: Impacts of industry on the Environment

We all know that environment in simple terms means the surroundings or conditions in which persons, animals, or plants lives or operates. There is a direct relationship between environment and economic development. Economic development without environmental considerations can cause serious environmental damage in turn impairing the quality of life of present and future generations.

Haloui & Yang (2024) argued that the Environmental impacts are changes in the natural or built environment, resulting directly from an activity, that can have adverse and consequential effects on the air, land, water, fish, and wildlife or the inhabitants of the ecosystem. Pollution, contamination, or destruction that occurs as a consequence of an action that can have short-term or long-term ramifications is considered an environmental impact.

Most adverse environmental impacts also have a direct link to public health and quality of life issues. Industrialization has the potential to help achieve a variety of social objectives, at the same time, industrial processes can have negative environmental impacts. Industrial processes play a major role in the degradation of the global environment. In industrialized countries, environmental regulation and new technologies are reducing the environmental impact per unit produced, but industrial activities and growing demand are still putting pressures on the environment and the natural resource base. In developing countries, a double environmental effect is occurring: old environmental problems, such as deforestation and soil degradation, remain largely unsolved. At the same time, new problems linked to industrialization are emerging, such as rising greenhouse gas emissions, air and water pollution, growing volumes of waste, desertification and chemicals pollution. Any business or developmental activity has a substantial impact on the environment (Gibbs, 2003).

The manufacture of products involves extracting raw materials from the environment and processing them to produce saleable items. As a result of the production process, various forms of waste (solid, liquid and gaseous) enter the environment.

Also, the activities surrounding the manufacturing process, such as maintenance of plant and infrastructure and the packaging and transport of goods, all have environmental impacts.

In addition to the above, the products that are produced will eventually be disposed of and enter the environment as waste. The provision of services also results in a significant environmental impact. Service companies use various products and also energy to deliver their services, both of which result in waste entering the environment. The provision of services also entails resource exploitation whilst rendering environment unstable.

Environmental protection

Healthy environmental systems not only improve natural systems, but also human wellbeing-based public health systems. Furthermore, applying and developing environmental engineering techniques and knowledge to solve environmental issues such as pollution, and public health issues such as hazardous risk prevention, is crucial. Accordingly, environmental engineering approaches to solutions are fundamental to maintaining healthy environmental systems; and to reducing public health hazards, such as contamination-control, -treatment, and - prevention (e.g., water, air, soil), for hazard exposure reduction. Environmental engineering studies investigate, analyze, and predict with suitable environmental models, how exposure to hazardous materials occurs in various environments. In doing so, environmental engineering studies contribute to solving environmental challenges by producing valuable analytical insights that engage environmental management; and workable engineering solutions to reduce the negative impacts of human activities on the environment and contribute to the protection of our environment.

Environmental protection refers to any activity to maintain or restore the quality of environmental media through preventing the emission of pollutants or reducing the presence of polluting substances in environmental media. It may consist of:

- i. Changes in characteristics of goods and services.
- ii. Changes in consumption patterns.
- iii. Changes in production techniques.
- iv. Treatment or disposal of residuals in separate environmental protection facilities,
- v. Recycling.

Prevention of Degradation of the Landscape and Ecosystems

Different approaches are used to assure environmental protection:

Environment Management

Environment Management is an attempt to control human impact on and interaction with the environment in order to preserve natural resources. It primarily stresses on finding solution to practical problems that people face in cohabitation with nature, resource exploitation, and waste production. Environmental management focuses on the improvement of human welfare for present and future generation. It implies not only a mere management of environment but it is essentially the management of various activities with intolerable constraints imposed by the environment itself and with full consideration of ecological factors. Environmental management is closely linked with issues regarding sustainable economic growth, ensuring fair and equitable distribution of resources, and conserving natural resources for future generations. Environmental management is a response to human actions considering the increasing seriousness and significance of today's disastrous human impact on natural ecosystems.

Importance of Environmental Management

Effective Utilization of Resources: Resources are limited, if we don't use them properly, they will get exhausted very soon. For appropriate and reasonable use of resources, environment management is necessary. It is our basic responsibility to create an accurate coordination and equilibrium between our needs and procedure of environment. For sustainable development: Environmental management is required for development without destruction or overuse of natural resources and to reduce pollution and degradation of nature. Considering the welfare of future generations, proper decisions regarding use of environment are necessary.

To decide the limiting line between environment and development: Environmental Management is essential to draw a line of limit for development and environment. For E.g. If our development needs to

lead to global warming or depletion of the ozone layer, then we must not use the materials, and modify our way of development. We may adopt the policy of afforestation.

For economic need and value: Environmental Management is required to give new directions to our economic needs and values, at the same time to maintain clean environment. To reduce disasters: Environmental Management reduces the risk of disasters like flooding, forest fire, earthquakes, desertification, transport accidents, Global warming, etc. We need to explore the link between environmental system and disasters and also the synergies between man-made and natural disasters.

Environmental management Models:

According to their principles environmental models can be divided into 3:

- i. Traditional environmental management based on terminal control: Terminal control, also known as terminal treatment, means before the terminal of the production process or the waste discharge into the nature, take a series of physical, chemical or biological measures to reduce the total amount emissions into the environment.
- ii. Environmental management model based on pollution prevention: Pollution prevention (P2) is a strategy for reducing the amount of waste created and released into the environment, particularly by industrial facilities, agriculture, or consumers. Many large corporations view P2 as a method of improving the efficiency and profitability of production processes by waste reduction and technology advancements. It includes:
 - a. Source reduction
 - b. Waste reduction
 - c. Circular economy
- iii. Pollution Prevention Environmental planning and management of pollution prevention model implementation process

Environmental management systems

As a pollution prevention approach Environmental System Management (ESM) is considered as a powerful tool for managing the adverse impacts of activities of an organization on the environment aspects it is generally regarded as proactive tool of corporate environmental management. An environmental management system Serves as a process, to improve environmental performance and information mainly "design, pollution control and waste minimization, training, reporting to top management, and the setting of goals.it also provides a systematic way of managing an organization's environmental affairs It Is the aspect of the organization's overall management structure that addresses immediate and long-term impacts of its products, services and processes on the environment. environmental management system assists with planning, controlling and monitoring policies in an organization.

The system follows a repeating cycle. The organization first commits to an environmental policy, then uses its policy as a basis for establishing a plan, which sets objectives and targets for improving environmental performance. The next step is implementation. After that, the organization evaluates its environmental performance to see whether the objectives and targets are being met. If targets are not being met, corrective action is taken. The results of this evaluation are then reviewed by top management to see if the environmental management system is working. Management revisits the environmental policy and sets new targets in a revised plan. The company then implements the revised plan and the cycle repeats, and continuous improvement occurs (Gibbs, 2003).

Industrial Ecology:

The concept of Industrial ecology is an environmental concept which was developed by researchers to improve the level of environmental management across the globe. The concept of Industrial ecology attempts to induce balance and cooperation between industrial processes and environmental sustainability, to the extent that neither violates the other. This approach, thus, has an aim of developing industrial processes that minimize the waste of materials and pollutants in materials, according to the cradle-to-cradle concept. Industrial ecology arises from the perception that human economic activity is to a large extent causing unacceptable changes in basic environmental support systems. As applied to the manufacturing sector, this systems-oriented concept often suggests that industrial design and

manufacturing processes are not performed in isolation from their surroundings, but rather are influenced by them and, in turn, influence them, enthrusing a systemic relationship (Gibbs, 2003).

In industrial ecology, economic systems are viewed not in isolation from their surrounding systems, but in connection with them. Industrial ecology often seeks to optimize the total materials cycle from virgin material to finished material to component, to product, to waste products, and to ultimate disposal. It is considered to be a field of study that focuses on the stages of the process of production of products (goods and services) from a point of view of nature, trying to mimic a natural system by conserving and ensuring that resources are being recycled and reused.

Industrial ecology often sees the industry as a man-made ecosystem that operates in a similar way to the natural ecosystems we have, where the waste or by product of one process is used as an input into another process. Industrial ecology interacts with natural ecosystems and attempts to move from a linear to cyclical or closed loop system. Like natural ecosystems, industrial ecology is in a continual state of flux.

Main Features:

Industrial processes, from material extraction through to the product disposal, have an adverse impact upon the environment. Industrial ecology aims to reduce the level of environmental stress caused by industry at the same time encouraging innovation, resource efficiency and sustained growth. Industrial ecology acknowledges that industry will continue to operate and expand however, it supports industry that are more environmentally conscious and gives less burden to our planet. It views industrial sites as part of a wider ecology rather than just an external, solitary entity. Within the industrial ecology concept, industry interacts with nature and utilizes the wastes and by products of other industries as inputs into its own processes. Industrial ecology ranges from purely industrial ecosystems to purely natural ecosystems with a range of hybrid industrial/natural ecosystems in between. Covering both industrial management and technology, industrial ecology encompasses other sustainability concepts and tools such as material flows analysis; environmentally sound technologies; design for disassembly; and dematerialization.

Principles of industrial ecology

Several scholars have attempted to outline the basic principles of industrial ecology, however, the principles of industrial ecology as defined by Tibbs (1992) seems to be more encompassing, we shall consider them briefly:

- i. Create industrial ecosystems – close the loop; view waste as a resource; create partnerships with other industries to trade by-products which are used as inputs to other processes.
- ii. Balance industrial inputs and outputs to natural levels – Manage the environmental-industrial interface; increase knowledge of ecosystem behavior, recovery time and capacity; increase knowledge of how and when industry can interact with natural ecosystems and the limitations.
- iii. Dematerialization of industrial output – Use fewer virgin materials and energy by becoming more resource efficient; reuse materials or substituting more environmentally friendly materials; do more with less.
- iv. Improve the efficiency of industrial processes – Redesign products, processes, equipment; reuse materials to conserve resources.
- v. Energy use – Incorporate energy supply within the industrial ecology; use alternative sources of energy that have less or no impact upon the environment.
- vi. Align policies with the industrial ecology concept – Incorporate environment and economics into organizational, national and international policies; internalize the externalities; use economic instruments to encourage a move towards industrial ecology; use a more appropriate discount rate; use a more comprehensive index to measure a nation's wealth rather than GNP.

Benefits of industrial ecology

As outlined by Cohen-Rosenthal, (2000) the benefits of industrial ecology include:

- i. Cost savings (materials purchasing, licensing fees, waste disposal fees, etc.);
- ii. Conserving natural resources by minimizing energy and materials usage.
- iii. Income generation through selling waste or by products.

Tools to Support Industrial Ecology:

Design for Environment and Life Cycle Design.

- i. Industrial Metabolism.
- ii. Life-cycle Assessment.
- iii. Cleaner Production & Pollution Prevention.
- iv. Energy Optimization.
- v. Dematerialization: Product-life extension.

Approaches to Industrial Ecology

Industrial ecology is the study of systemic relationships between society, the economy, and the natural environment. It focuses on the use of technology to reduce environmental impacts and reconcile human development with environmental stewardship while recognizing the importance of socioeconomic factors in achieving these goals.

Industrial ecology studies often quantify the use and cycling of materials and energy in society and their exchanges (extraction and emissions) with nature. Such analyses focus on different levels and scales, from eco-industrial parks and cities to nations and the global economy.

The term 'industrial ecology' derives from a recognition that economic systems (such as manufacturing processes) and ecosystems are similar. Industrial ecology draws on various concepts from ecology, including material and energy cycles, complex adaptive systems, and ecological networks. Erkman (1997) highlighted the similarities between industrial and natural ecology in their definition of the field:

Industrial ecology intersects multiple disciplines, including the natural sciences, engineering, and the social sciences. It also builds on various concepts such as the Tragedy of the Commons, Spaceship Earth, and Sustainable Development. It offers a growing set of scientifically rigorous quantitative methods and approaches, and today increasingly involves applied data science and scientific programming. Methods and approaches used in industrial ecology include:

- a. Material flow analysis - the quantification of mass and energy flows in systems ranging from industrial plants to the global economy, including in temporally dynamic states.
- b. Life cycle assessment - the systemic analysis of environmental flows and related impacts that arise throughout the life cycles of products and services, from raw material extraction to end-of-life disposal.
- c. Environmentally extended input-output analysis - a method to quantify environmental footprints based on the exchanges between economic sectors, and with the environment.
- d. Industrial symbiosis - the study of the exchange of waste as a resource among nearby industrial facilities, akin to synergistic physical relationships among biological species.
- e. Other approaches, such as socioeconomic metabolism for national economies, urban metabolism for cities, and the analysis of important socioeconomic factors such as consumer behaviour, business models, and public policy.

Industrial ecology has contributed to various ideas about economic systems that aim to improve resource efficiency, i.e. minimizing waste and maximizing the services delivered by using resources. These ideas have culminated in the concept of the circular economy, which became widespread in the 2010s. Today, industrial ecology provides scientifically rigorous methodologies, tools, and approaches for understanding and applying circular economy practices.

Constraints and Incentives for Industrial Ecology:

Industrial ecology cannot be studied and optimized in isolation from the human institutions of various kinds that promote or constrain the materials or energy flows:

- (i) Engineering excellence can often promote cyclic behavior within the manufacturing node by designing processes to promote materials reuse.
- (ii) The desire to avoid toxic wastes may promote process changes to reduce the quantity of wastes or (better) to substitute materials or components that result in less toxic or nontoxic wastes.
- (iii) The economic system may make it difficult to raise capital to alter a process and render it more efficient, that is, to improve its cyclic nature.

- (iv) Taxation may promote raw materials flows or import-export flows that are contrary to cyclization of the industrial ecosystem.
- (v) Government regulations may make reuse of materials so difficult that enhanced waste flow is in fact encouraged.
- (vi) The price system, by failing to include relevant externalities in prices and costs, may preclude adoption of industrial ecology by manufacturers and producers.
- (vii) The standard of living of the consumer may encourage long product use or, alternatively, may promote early product disposal.
- (viii) The rapid rate of technological evolution and obsolescence contributes to an enhanced waste stream.

Key Findings of the Study

1. The study with reference to the impacts of industries on the environment found out that, there is a direct relationship between environment and economic development. Economic development without environmental considerations can cause serious environmental damage in turn impairing the quality of life of present and future generations. The study further observed that most adverse environmental impacts also have a direct link to public health and quality of life issues. Similarly, the study established that industrialization has the potential to help achieve a variety of social objectives, at the same time, industrial processes can have negative environmental impacts. Industrial processes play a major role in the degradation of the global environment.
2. Furthermore, the study with regards to the importance, models, and system of environmental management observed that, environmental management is required to give new directions to our economic needs and values, at the same time to maintain clean environment. To reduce disasters; environmental management reduces the risk of disasters like flooding, forest fire, earthquakes, desertification, transport accidents, Global warming, etc. While on the models of environmental management, the study outlines the models to include: traditional environmental management based on terminal control, environmental management model based on pollution prevention, and pollution prevention environmental planning and management of pollution prevention model implementation process. Conversely, on the environmental management systems, the study established that environmental management system, serves as a process, to improve environmental performance and information mainly "design, pollution control and waste minimization, training, reporting to top management, and the setting of goals.it also provides a systematic way of managing an organization's environmental affairs.
3. Conversely, the study with reference to the concept and principles of industrial ecology states that, industrial ecology arises from the perception that human economic activity is to a large extent causing unacceptable changes in basic environmental support systems. For instance, as it applies to the manufacturing sector, this systems-oriented concept often suggests that industrial design and manufacturing processes are not performed in isolation from their surroundings, but rather are influenced by them and, in turn, influence them, enthusing a systemic relationship (Gibbs, 2003). While the study identify the principles of industrial ecology as defined by Tibbs (1992 to include: create industrial ecosystems, balance industrial inputs and outputs to natural levels, dematerialization of industrial output, improve the efficiency of industrial processes, energy use, and align policies with the industrial ecology concept.
4. Conclusively, the study with regards to the approaches, constraints and incentives for industrial ecology found out that, industrial ecology focuses on the use of technology to reduce environmental impacts and reconcile human development with environmental stewardship while recognizing the importance of socioeconomic factors in achieving these goals. While on the incentives to industrial ecology the study established that, industrial ecology can often promote cyclic behavior within the manufacturing node by designing processes to promote materials reuse, may promote process changes to reduce the quantity of wastes or (better) to substitute materials or components that result in less toxic or nontoxic wastes, and it may promote raw materials flows or import-export flows that are contrary to cyclization of the industrial ecosystem.

CONCLUSION

This study on "Environmental Management through Industrial Ecology" highlights the potential of industrial ecology principles to transform industrial practices and promote sustainability. By applying industrial ecology strategies, industries can reduce environmental impacts, conserve natural resources, and improve their overall sustainability performance. The study's findings emphasize the importance of adopting a holistic approach to environmental management, one that considers the interconnections between industrial activities and the environment.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

For Industries

1. Adopt circular economy principles: Implement waste reduction and recycling programs to minimize waste and promote resource efficiency.
2. Implement eco-design: Design products and processes with environmental sustainability in mind, considering the entire product life cycle.
3. Invest in cleaner production: Adopt cleaner production technologies and practices to reduce environmental impacts.

For Policymakers

1. Develop supportive policies: Create policies and regulations that encourage industries to adopt sustainable practices and invest in environmental management.
2. Provide incentives: Offer incentives for industries that adopt environmentally friendly practices and technologies.
3. Promote education and training: Support education and training programs that build capacity for sustainable industrial practices.

For Future Research

1. Conduct case studies: Conduct in-depth case studies of industries that have successfully implemented industrial ecology principles.
2. Develop metrics and indicators: Develop standardized metrics and indicators to measure the effectiveness of industrial ecology practices.
3. Explore new technologies: Investigate the potential of emerging technologies to support sustainable industrial practices.

By implementing these recommendations, industries and policymakers can work together to promote sustainability, reduce environmental impacts, and ensure a more sustainable future.

REFERENCES

- Allenby, B. and Cooper, W.E. (1994) 'Understanding industrial ecology from a biological systems perspective', *Total Quality Environmental Management*, Spring 1994, pp.343–354
- Andrews, E. S., & White, M. A. (2003). The value of industrial ecology for environmental policy. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 6(3), 155-167.
- Burström, F. and Korhonen, J. (2001) 'Municipalities and industrial ecology: reconsidering municipal environmental management', *Sustainable Development*, Vol. 9, No. 1 February 2001, pp.36–46.
- Cohen-Rosenthal, E. (2000) 'A walk on the human side of industrial ecology', *American Behavioral Scientist*, Vol. 44, No. 2, October, 2000, pp.245–264.
- Ehrenfeld, J.R. (2000) 'Industrial ecology: paradigm shift or normal science?', *American Behavioral Scientist*, Vol. 44, No. 2, October 2000, pp.229–244.
- Gibbs, D.C. (2003) 'Trust and networking in inter-firm relations: the case of eco-industrial development', *Local Environment*, Vol. 18, No. 3, pp.222–236.
- Guinée, J. B. (Ed.). (2002). *Handbook on life cycle assessment: Operational guide to the ISO standards*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Graedel, T. E., & Allenby, B. R. (2003). *Industrial ecology*. Prentice Hall.

- Haloui I. & Yang L. (2024), Integrating Environmental Management and Industrial Ecology: Approaches, Tools, and Models for Sustainable Development. *International Journal of Advance Research*. 12(09), 453-466
- Hertwich, E. G. (2005). Life cycle approaches to sustainable consumption: A critical review. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 39(13), 4673-4684
- Hilty, L. M., Arnfalk, P., Erdmann, L., Goodman, J., Lehmann, M., Wäger, P. A., & Widmer, R. (2006). The relevance of information and communication technologies for environmental sustainability—A prospective simulation study. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 21(11), 1618-1629.
- Korhonen, J. and Strachan, P.A. (2004) 'Editorial: Towards progress in industrial ecology', *Progress in Industrial Ecology*, Vol. 1, Nos. 1/2/3, pp.1–23
- Korhonen, J. (2004) 'Industrial ecology in the strategic sustainable development model: Strategic applications of industrial ecology', *Journal of Cleaner Production special issue 'Applications of Industrial Ecology'*
- Lifset, R. J. (Ed.). (2014). *Industrial ecology and sustainable engineering*. Oxford University Press.
- Tibbs H. B.C., (1992) *Industrial Ecology-An Agenda for Environmental Management*. Pollution Prevention Review/Spring.
- Salmi, O. (2003) 'Development and path dependence in the industrial system of the Kola Peninsula', in Hukkinen (Ed.): *Technology, Society, Environment*, Helsinki University of Technology, Espoo, Otamedeia Oy, Finland, pp.29–46.
- Spengler, J. D., Sexton, K., & Wilson, R. (2007). *Environmental health: Sciences, decisions, and the risks of chemicals*. John Wiley & Sons
- United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). (2002). *Industrial ecology and sustainable engineering*. Nairobi, Kenya: UNEP